

Fatigue Behaviour of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Epoxy Composite Materials with Edge Notch

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ABSTRACT

A study of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite specimens with 0 ply and $\pm 45^\circ$ ply (unnotched and with edge notched normal to loading direction) was carried out under tension-tension cycle loading. Fatigue behaviour and failure modes were investigated and compared with static tests (1). A variety of techniques (acoustic emission, two types of strain extensometer, scanning electron microscope, etc.) were used to examine the damage of specimens.

The results of fatigue experiments show the fatigue lives of these carbon/epoxy composites are rather long. The fatigue strengths are quite well. Due to local damage, in certain great number of cycles both the frequency and the stiffness of specimen decrease with increasing cycle number. Beyond initial damage specimens can still sustain a great number of cycles at high stress levels. The residual strength still remains rather high. When notched specimens are axially fatigue loaded in tension-tension, at the tip of notch, cracks propagate along the direction of fiber. Further cracks develop along with cyclic loads. After the first crack occurs, specimens can sustain a long time fatigue till completely fracture. Carbon/epoxy have good damage-tolerance. Just before specimen failure, temperature of these carbon/epoxy materials has risen considerably. Among fatigue failure modes delamination is most severe. For $\pm 45^\circ$ ply coupon specimens, interlaminar shear control failure. The mechanism of fatigue damage is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials as structural components under cyclic loading are becoming increasingly widespread. Fatigue behaviour of fiber reinforced composites have many features compared with metals. It is an important difference from each other. The fatigue failure mechanism of composites is more complicated than that of metals. It depends on several factors including the materials constituents, the fibers arrays, the interfacial bonding strength, the loading condition, etc. A group fatigue investigations of glass fiber reinforced composites have been carried out. Some fatigue failure studies of advanced carbon fiber reinforced composites have also been

done (e.g.(2-5)), but less than the former, and even less are the studies on notch effect of that materials. In order to make full use of the good damage tolerance of carbon fiber reinforced composite materials, fatigue failure mechanism of this composite needs to be investigated.

In this paper, through analyses of a series of experimental results, the fatigue behaviour of carbon/epoxy composite materials of 0° and ±45° ply specimens with edge notch is studied and compared with static tests (1). The fatigue strength and fatigue life under tension-tension cycle loading are determined. The mechanism of fatigue failure of unnotched and notched specimens are discussed.

MATERIALS AND SPECIMENS

The specimens used in this investigation were made of L180 or S220 carbon fibers and 648 epoxy matrix. The fiber volume fraction was 61%. The thickness of each ply was 0.12mm. All laminates were formed by the heated press method and cured with FB₄ ethylamine. Uniaxially aligned fiber composite laminates were sawn and ground to zero ply specimens. ±45° ply specimens were cut from cross-ply. Due to the difference in constituents, ply angle and dimensions, the specimens can be divided into A,B,C,D four groups, each group involved unnotched and edge notched specimens. Details of the specimen are given in Table 1. The notch is normal to the direction of loading as shown in Fig.1. The edge notch was made by line electrode spark cutting. The width of notch is 0.2mm and the length is 3mm.

Table 1 Summary of Specimen and Static Strengths

Spec. Type	Constituents	Lay-up	Unnotched or Notched	Nominal Area (mm ²) Gross	Sectional Net	Mean Static Tensile Strengths MPa	Ultimate
A-1 A-I	Carbon S220/ epoxy 648	(0) _n	unnotched notched	22.5 22.5	18	1109	1135
B-1 B-I	Carbon L180/ epoxy 648	(0) ₁	unnotched notched	14.4 14.4	10.8	844	844
C-1 C-I	Carbon S220/ epoxy 648	(±45) ₅	unnotched notched	39.6 39.6	33	96	98
D-1 D-I	Carbon L180/ epoxy 648	(±45) ₅	unnotched notched	21.6 21.6	16.2	93.2	96

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The fatigue tests were carried out in a PIQ2Z fatigue machine using tension-tension cycle. The testing frequency was 50HZ-60HZ. Apparatus used are shown in Fig.2. One kind of displacement transducers and X-Y recorder were used to measure and record the deformation of specimen, from which stiffness variation were determined. Another kind of transducer (∩ shape) and microscope were used to measure and examine the opening displacement of notch during the test (Fig.1,3).

A SFS-4 Acoustic Emission System was used to monitor the process of fatigue damage. This is an advanced technique used in fatigue testing of composites. Automatic threshold was used to filter noise during cyclic loading testing, so acoustic emission signals were detectable. The probe with 120KHZ frequency was placed on the specimen using grease to ensure proper acoustic coupling (Fig.3). Through the transducer acoustic emission

events and their cumulative counts were obtained. The acoustic emission counts and cumulative counts—cyclic number curves were plotted automatically. It presents matrix creaking, fiber breakage, delamination, etc. Which provides a indication of behaviour of carbon/epoxy undergoing a fatigue testing. In addition, interface failure and cross-section were examined by means of scanning electron microscope.

THE RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTS

Fatigue Behaviour of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Epoxy O° Ply Specimens

Unnotched Specimen of O° Ply. Tension-tension axial load fatigue at various maximum cycle stress level S (different percentage of mean static ultimate strength (σ_b)) were tested. Each point represents the logarithm of N at a certain S for one specimen. S - N curve was obtained (Fig.4). The data in fig.4 agree well with the linear. Which has not a evident fatigue limit as in metals. The failure strength was defined as the maximum cyclic stress under which the specimen could be survived in 10^5 - 10^7 cycles for practically request. For these specimens, when stress levels at 25%, 40%, 50% till $N=10^7$ specimens did not failure. At maximum cycle stress level higher than 60% of static strength (σ_b) specimens fail. Some specimens at 65% stress level did not failure yet. Under axial loading specimen could be survived in 10^7 cycles and maintains rather high residual strength. For example, specimen A-1-8 was loaded at maximum stress 60% σ_b . After 10^7 cycle, its residual strength σ_r could reach 62% σ_b . For cycle loaded carbon/epoxy composites due to local damage the stiffness changed before fatigue fracture. The stiffness degrading rate was different at various stress levels. In this experiment stiffness degrading range from 20 to 40% (compared with the stiffness of specimen under static loading to mean stress). Due to the damping characteristic and fatigue damage, frequency decreased in 10^5 - 10^7 cycles. At various stress levels, reduction of frequency is from 0.2HZ to 1.3HZ. In fatigue damage of O° ply specimen, epoxy matrix crack started from free side edge, followed cycles increased, a small bundle of fibers were separate, then, delamination was appeared. When delamination getting serious along side edges, longitudinal cracks propagated from middle to the ends of the specimens, the temperature was increased and finally specimen was broken completely. For example, specimen B-1-5, mean static ultimate strength $\sigma_b = 844$ Mpa, the maximum cyclic stress is 60% σ_b , when cycle number exceeded 10^5 , stiffness began decreased (Fig.5), at 5×10^5 cycles upper side edge of specimen appeared matrix crack and some fibers bundle debonded, then, frequency began decreased. When $N=10^6$, small strip separated, as $N=1.3 \times 10^6$ side edge of specimen delaminated obviously, then, $N=1.6 \times 10^6$ debonding widening occurred and temperature of specimen rose to $30^{\circ}C$. The longitudinal crack propagated from middle section to the upper end of specimen. Complete failure happened at cyclic number of 2×10^6 . Only the up clamp of metal fixture was heated by the failure upper part of specimen, the lower clamp was not heated. It is show that carbon/epoxy composite under cyclic loading have got considerable temperature rising just before specimen was seriously damaged.

O° Ply Specimen with Edge Notch. The S - N curve is linear also. Some specimens failed at 60% stress level at 10^7 cycles, but some specimens at this case still survived. So the fatigue strength of these specimen was considered 60%. The cumulate damage leaded to reductions in modulus and frequency. Decrease of frequency is less than that of as unnotched specimen. Because the notched specimen has defect (notch) already and the damage leaded damping change is not as obvious as that in unnotched specimen. The process of failure started off with notch opening, then longitudinal crack occur at the tip of the notch. When cycle number getting larger the notch opened gradually and crack propagated along the fiber direction. Eventually cracks extend to the end causing complete failure in specimen. For example, in specimen A-I-7, the static ultimate strength is 1109 Mpa, maximum cyclic stress $S=60\% \sigma_b$, when specimen subjected to mean stress S_m and under cyclic loading, the notch opened from 0.2mm to

0.3mm. As $N=3 \times 10^5$, at the tip of notch longitudinal crack occurred. When $N \approx 10^6$, cracks propagated and widened. In the vicinity of crack tip appeared loose state. When cycles reached 4×10^6 , the notch opened to 0.45mm and the longitudinal crack spread to 2.3mm. As $N=8 \times 10^6$, the temperature of specimen rose, notch opened to 0.56mm. The stiffness had decreased 40% and frequency had reduced 0.2Hz. Finally specimen was longitudinally separated and complete failure happened.

When first longitudinal crack occurred at notch tip the stress or cycles were usually even lower than those at specimen failure. As fatigue loading was as high as $70\% \sigma_u$, in some specimens crack occurred at notch tip when the load exceeded the half of maximum stress. But still could reach the maximum stress and the high power of cycles. If stress level was not very high, tip crack occurred in 10^5 cycles, however also reached 8×10^6 or 10^7 cycles.

Fatigue of Carbon/Epoxy $\pm 45^\circ$ Angle Specimens

Unnotched Specimen of $\pm 45^\circ$ Ply. Under different maximum stresses subjected cyclic loading, S-N curve was obtained as Fig. 7. When the maximum cycle stress levels were 60% and 70% specimens failure happened at cyclic number 1.4×10^6 and 7.7×10^5 respectively. When specimens subjected to maximum cycle stress $S=50\% \sigma_u$, they could survive till 10^7 cycles. Their residual strength σ_r is 46% σ_u . Referred to the S-N curve, the fatigue strength is considered being higher than 50%. Generally, modulus degenerated about 24-30% after 10^6 cycles. Frequency reduction was less than 1 Hz. Fatigue failure started from shear debonding, then the surface crack occurred and propagated along $\pm 45^\circ$ direction. Shear delamination developed from layer to layer until all plies cracked in 45° (Fig.8). After first ply initial damage specimen could still sustained a great number of cycles. For example, specimen D-1-4 was subjected to 60% cycle stress level, delamination of surface ply occurred at 1.38×10^6 cycles. After another 10^4 cycles first ply emerged 45° crack, then, every layer debonded and cracked, finally, specimen failed at 1.4×10^6 cycles.

$\pm 45^\circ$ Ply Specimen with Edge Notch. Under tension-tension fatigue loading, the notch opened from 0.2mm to 0.4mm. The notch opening displacement was less than that of the 0° ply specimens ($d=0.7$ mm), this is due to restraint of the fibers plus and minus 45° angle plied. As cycles increased, the crack occurred at the notch-tip and propagated along $\pm 45^\circ$ direction. All layers debonded and the crack extended across the width of the specimen from notch-tip. The fracture always occurred at the section where notch located. But may be any position in unnotched specimens. Acoustic emission was used to monitor the process of fatigue damage. Correlate with microscope observation the acoustic emission spectrol can be analyses. Fig.9(a) shows the variety of acoustic emission event increment and cumulative data of $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimen with notch C-I-7 during the failure process. When specimen is subjected to fatigue loaded and the notch opened, acoustic emission signals of small energy release appeared. At 5.2×10^5 cycles, the signal enhanced. Specimen started debond, damage constantly emerged causing the signals appear unceasingly, some larger some smaller. When cyclic number was 1.3×10^5 event signal increased one time as former, which showing crack occur at notch tip, developed from ply to ply, acoustic emission signal wealth. At 2.1×10^7 cycles, event signals rose suddenly, all plies delaminate and specimen failure. Total cumulation of acoustic emission represent the total energy release in specimen. Fig.9(b) shows the acoustic emission counts during fatigue failure stage of specimen C-I-8.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

S-N Curves of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Epoxy Composite Materials

S-N curves are obtained from experimental results. The relationship

of cycle stress and logarithm of cycle number is linear. for both 0° ply and $\pm 45^\circ$ ply. The data of linear S-N curves may be represented by an equation.

$$S = \bar{\sigma}_b - b \log N \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_b$ is the one-cycle intercept of the S-N curves i.e. the mean static ultimate strength and b is the slope of the line i.e. the decreasing value of cycle stress per decade of cycles. For example, in Fig.4 for the S-N curve of 0° ply with edge notch specimens type A-I, b is 62. Fig.7, the S-N curve of $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimens type D-1, b is 7. For type C $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimens, b are 7 and 8 for unnotched and notched specimens respectively. Thus, the fatigue stress under any certain cycle number can be predicted by S-N equation (1). The ratio $\bar{\sigma}_b/b$ represents the rate of fatigue degradation of the materials. In this experiment, the S-N curve of type D-1 $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimens with a ratio of 14, indicates a loss of one fourteenth of the $\bar{\sigma}_b$ per decade of cycles. The S-N curve of type A-I 0° ply specimens with a ratio of 17.6, indicates a loss of 1/17.6 of $\bar{\sigma}_b$ per decade of cycles. In other words, type D-1 $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens lose about 7% of $\bar{\sigma}_b$ per decade of cycles and type A-I 0° specimen lose about 6% of $\bar{\sigma}_b$ per decade of cycles. Type C $\pm 45^\circ$ ply unnotched and edge notched specimens lose 7% and 8.6% of $\bar{\sigma}_b$ per decade of cycles respectively (Fig.7). These data show that $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimens have slightly rapid degradation than 0° ply specimens and $\pm 45^\circ$ ply notch specimens are slightly rapid degradation than unnotched specimens (Fig.4) Although the carbon fiber of type C and type D are not the same but they have the same degradating ratio. Besides, it is shown that the rate of fatigue degradation of carbon fiber reinforced composites are lower than that of glass fiber reinforced composites ($\approx 10\%$) (6).

These S-N curves which show no flattening trend at 10^7 cycles, it means that there no definite fatigue limit in carbon/epoxy as that in metals. Generally, composites material fail under 10^6 or 10^7 cycles corresponding maximum cyclic stress is considered as fatigue strength. In this region, the load is variated a little, then cycles may be more varied reverse.

Fatigue Failure Behaviour of Carbon Reinforced Epoxy Composite Materials

The deformation of carbon fiber is even less than that of epoxy matrix. For this reason, in carbon/epoxy cracks occur at the interface or in matrix under fatigue loading in certain cycles. This initial damage of composites has no important effect on fatigue life, they can still sustain a great number of cycles (e.g. 10^6-10^7) at certain cycle stress. When damage cumulation reached a certain degree, cracks increased and extended and interface debond. Finally specimen fractured. Because tensile strength of 0° ply specimen is higher than interlaminar shear strength under tensile fatigue. When longitudinal crack propagates interlaminar stress increases causing delaminate failure. As far as the $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimen is concerned, shearing failure is a control factor of fatigue rupture. After initial damage, 0° ply can sustain longer fatigue life than $\pm 45^\circ$ ply. In the $\pm 45^\circ$ off-axis laminate specimen under tensile fatigue, the fatigue shear properties also can be inspected as that in static tension. However, in this $\pm 45^\circ$ ply coupon specimen crack started from free edge and was interlaminar. Consequently, it caused considerable shear stress. For tube specimen loaded uniformly, there is no high edge interlaminar shear stress. As a result, the shear strength of coupon specimen is lower than that of tube specimen. This distinctness of high module carbon fiber composites is more great than glass fiber composites.

Since fatigue failure was caused by cumulate damage, cracks increase gradually. Thus, specimen usually present loose slightly and debonding along the thickness is most obvious. That is the different from static tensile fracture. However, as far as the fracture surface is concerned, there is no marked difference between fatigue and static tension.

Microscopical observation of fracture surface (Fig.8, Fig.9) show the failure mode as following: the matrix cracked, some fibers broken and the

interface debonding. They present the materials loose and delaminate evidently than under static tension.

Fatigue Damage Mechanism of Carbon/Epoxy With Edge Notch

In carbon/epoxy 0° ply and $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimens with edge notch subjected to tensile fatigue loading, initial damage started from notch opening. Due to the shear stress in loaded direction, the first crack occurred at notch-tip in certain cycles. Crack did not propagate along the notch direction but was in the fiber direction. Crack number, length and width extended with increasing cycles. The stress or cycles of first crack occur even lower than those of specimen fracture. After first tip crack appeared $\pm 45^\circ$ ply specimen could sustain less cycles than 0° ply specimen. The rate of fatigue degradation of notched specimen is slightly rapid than that of unnotched specimen (Fin.47). That is due to the fact that crack at notch-tip occur earlier and damage cumulates more rapidly. However, the notch has no severe effect on fatigue properties. The notch has no substantially effect on the stress at the unnotch portion. Only net cross-sectional area of specimen is considered to be subjected to fatigue loading. As a result of continuous cyclic loading, tip crack extend longer than in static tension. Because of the boundary delamination stress concentration is less than that in static tension. Notched composite specimen under cyclic loading can release more energy acoustic emission signals than metals and unnotched specimens of composites (Fig.9).

The Effect of Temperature Rise During Fatigue Testing on Carbon/Epoxy Composites

Due to the viscoelastic characteristics of the matrix and some damages of the composite, so that during fatigue process the temperature of specimen rises as a result of energy consume. Because the stiffness of carbon fiber is rather high and property of epoxy is good, carbon/epoxy composites do not have a noticeable temperature rise due to viscoelasticity. Just before failure specimen delaminated severely and heat is created by crack surface friction. Temperature reaches about 30°C before specimen fracture. The temperature rising is connected with failure directly. Specimens are heated only in failure region. There are no considerable increase in temperature at the rest parts of specimens because the thermal conductivity of carbon/epoxy is small. During fatigue testing of carbon/epoxy specimens, the temperature rise was not high and occur only in a short time. Thus its effect on fatigue property is not as serious as that in GFRP (temperature rise is about 60°C).

The results mentioned above show that the tensile fatigue strength of a carbon/epoxy composite with 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ ply at 10^7 cycles varied between 50 and 60 per cent of the mean static ultimate strength, they are higher than that of metal (28-40%) and glass/epoxy ($\approx 35\%$) that we had done. Initial damage in these composites can not lead to rapid failure. Carbon/epoxy in fatigue-resistant application is superior to metal and GFRP. For primary components in critical applications the cycles at which the stiffness of composites decrease evidently should be considered as design cycle. For general components the cycles at fracture was considered as fatigue limit. Carbon/epoxy has good damage-tolerance. Specimens with notch have no marked effect on fatigue properties. This demonstrates the low notch sensitivity of carbon/epoxy composites.

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Fig. 1 Specimen

Fig. 2 Apparatus

Fig. 3 Measuring instruments

Fig. 4 S-N curves for carbon S220/epoxy specimens (.R=0.2)

Fig. 5 Stiffness degradation of carbon L180/epoxy 648 specimen B-1-5 during fatigue loading

Fig. 6 Failure mode of 0° ply specimen

Fig.7 S-N curves for C/E±45° ply specimens (comparison of Type C and D) (R=0.1)

Fig.8 Failure mode of ±45° ply specimen

Fig. 9 (a) Specimen C-I-7 (b) Specimen C-I-8
Acoustic emission counts during fatigue test of ±45° ply specimen with edge notch

Fig. 10 (a) 0° ply specimen (b) ±45° ply specimen
Microscope observation of fracture surface